

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06
Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03
Funding Scheme: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions (RIA)

Grant Agreement no: 101057062

AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

Deliverable No. 3.6

G1 installed for testing

Contractual Submission Date: 30/06/2024

Actual Submission Date: 30/06/2024

Responsible partner: P9: GND

**Funded by
the European Union**

Grant agreement no.	101057062
Project full title	AIDAVA - AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

Deliverable number	D3.6
Deliverable title	G1 of the AIDAVA prototype
Type ¹	DEM
Dissemination level ²	PU
Work package number	WP3
Work package leader	P9 - GND
Author(s)	Bela Bihari, Daniel Dallos, Lorant Ferencz, Botond Kiss, Zsolt Mate, Alpar Tana (P9-GND) Isabelle de Zegher (P2 - b!lo) Remzi Celebi, Ensar Emir Erol (P1-UM)
Keywords	virtual assistant, data curation, real data, live testing

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The work of MID received funding by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SBFI), subvention contract 22.00093, REF-1131-52104.

Supported by a licence waiver from SNOMED International from a period of 2 years (2024 – 2025), on condition that SNOMED CT is not used and/or deployed commercially.

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1	25.06.2024	Document ready for internal review
V2	28.06.2024	Final Version

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
1 Introduction	5
2 Description of Activities	6
2.1 Development	6
2.2 Deployment	6
2.2.1 Hosting servers	6
2.3 Testing	6
3 Results & Discussion	7
3.1 Description of key functions of the systems (user manual)	7
3.1.1 First Access - Authentication	7
3.1.2 First Access - Mandatory Steps	8
3.1.3 Account recovery	8
3.1.4 Account Settings	9
3.1.5 Curation Flow	9
3.1.6 Import	10
3.1.7 Curation	10
3.1.8 Answer Questions - Patient	11
3.1.9 Answer Question - Curator	11
3.1.10 View your dossier (patient view)	12
3.1.11 Viewing the patient risk score (cardio specialist data users)	12
3.1.12 Viewing the Breast Cancer Registry federated queries across sites (BC data users)	13
3.1.13 Viewing the patient dossiers (all data users)	13
3.2 Testing results	14
3.2.1 Unit tests	14
3.2.2 Integration tests	14
3.2.3 User Acceptance tests	15
3.2.4 Testing non-functional requirements	16
3.3 Prototype deployment & availability	16
3.3.1 MUG - Medizinische Universitat Graz (MUG)	17
3.3.2 NEMC - Sihtasutus Pohja-estti Regionaalhaigla	18
3.3.3 Maastru	19
3.4 AIDAVA Support	19
4 Conclusion and next steps	21

List of Definitions

The definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [\[ref\]](#).

Executive Summary

AIDAVA is a prototype system that supports patients to (semi)automatically integrate and curate their personal health data. The prototype is focusing on hospital data and non-hospital data pooled through a Health Data Intermediary (HDI), across 2 use cases : monitoring of cardiac risk score across patients with myocardial infarction treated across 3 different hospitals and interoperability of queries across breast cancer registries federated across 3 different hospitals.

The system first allows patients to integrate all their data: non-hospital data from the HDI and hospital data and then helps the patient to curate these data into an interoperable and consistent format: the Personal Health Knowledge Graph. AIDAVA uses Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies to support automation in this curation process; if the AI tools cannot solve an issue, the systems initiate a dialogue with the users.

When the data are curated, AIDAVA can provide the patient's International Patient Summary (IPS), for CVD patients help cardiologists to compute a cardiac risk score, and for BC patients help researchers to answer queries across different sites.

Generation 1 of the prototype has been developed following the user requirements gathered in Work Package 1, and includes multiple curation tools that are integrated through dedicated containers. While a lot of the functionalities are provided in the frontend of the prototype, the curation tools provided in the backend - that were intended to be based on existing tools in G1 and then replaced in G2 by tools newly developed during the project - are suboptimal. We therefore already included some of the newly developed tools in G1; these tools will however require optimization (as planned) for G2.

The system has been rigorously tested, including unit tests for individual components, integration tests for combined functionality and mainly user tests conducted by GND's internal testers. It is being deployed across the 4 evaluation hospitals to undergo testing with real patients, with patient informed consent and following a strict evaluation protocol agreed by local Ethical committees. The results of this evaluation will be the basis of the update/improvement to be brought in Generation 2 of the prototype.

1 Introduction

The AIDAVA system is a highly distributed architecture comprising around 50 different running Docker containers, following the technical architecture defined in *Deliverable D3.1 VA architecture (Application and Technical)* and in accordance with the requirements provided in *Deliverable D3.2 Epics and user stories for G1*.

This deliverable describes the Generation 1 (G1) of the AIDAVA prototype ready for evaluation and testing defined in *Deliverable D1.4 Definition of assessment study including test scenarios & metrics*, approved by the respective ethical committees in the 4 organisations where the prototype will be formally tested with patients.

In Section 2, we briefly describe the different activities that took place during development and deployment. Section 3 provides a set of screen dumps from the application (in English), the results of the testing, the status of deployment across the 4 evaluation sites (in local language) and the support mechanism during the evaluation. Section 4 concludes with next steps.

2 Description of Activities

2.1 Development

Although the project was aimed at delivering a TRL6 prototype, the GND team opted for a professional, product-oriented software development process from the outset. This strategic decision was made to ensure that the final output would be a close-to-market solution, ready for further refinement and deployment in real-world applications. By adopting a rigorous development approach early on, the team aimed to reduce the gap between the prototype and a market-ready product, thereby accelerating the overall development timeline and improving the potential for successful commercialization.

The team followed a structured SDLC framework to plan, create, test, and deploy the software systematically. This approach ensured each development phase was executed properly and reviewed, maintaining high quality and mitigating risks.

Agile development practices were implemented to enhance flexibility and responsiveness. The team delivered incremental improvements, gathered feedback, and made adjustments promptly, aligning the product closely with user needs.

A strong emphasis on UX design ensured the software was intuitive. Prototyping and usability testing were integral, identifying and addressing usability issues early in development.

CI/CD automation reduced integration issues, accelerated feature delivery and bug fixes, and maintained software quality, ensuring rapid and reliable updates throughout the development lifecycle.

2.2 Deployment

To ensure seamless deployment and individual component management, we configured a CI/CD³ pipelines. This setup facilitates easy deployment of each separate component and allows for the efficient updating of various curation tools as necessary.

2.2.1 Hosting servers

The server requested for the project had the following configuration: 64GB RAM, 8-core CPU, and 1TB storage. These servers were provided by the medical partners within their infrastructure. Each instance can only be accessed by the medical partner and the GND team, to provide support in accordance with the ethical committee's agreement.

2.3 Testing

In preparation for the G1 evaluation, we conducted extensive testing to ensure the robustness and reliability of our system. Our testing process included unit tests for various individual components, integration tests to verify the connections between these components, and user tests using synthetic data provided by our medical partner.

³ continuous integration and continuous delivery/deployment

In Deliverable D3.2 Epics and user stories for G1, we also defined Acceptance Criteria for each user story. During the internal user testing phase, our focus was on complying with and fulfilling these criteria. This approach ensured that each aspect of the user experience met the predefined standards of functionality and performance, thereby validating both the usability and effectiveness of the system in real-world conditions.

3 Results & Discussion

3.1 Description of key functions of the systems (user manual)

This section provides the user manual (in English) provided to the AIDAVA user during the evaluation. The actual system has been translated in each local language (Estonian, German and Dutch). It is expected that the system is intuitive enough and does not require additional explanation after the first access. For the patient, the first access will be supported by a study nurse that will guide the patient through the different steps.

3.1.1 First Access - Authentication

First access

Step 1 Choose your language	Step 2 Access your account	Step 3 Set Password	Step 4 Verify your credentials by logging in

Read FAQ if you need to review this document

Figure 1. First Access - Authentication

3.1.2 First Access - Mandatory Steps

First access

Please review your profile data (name, gender, condition). This is mandatory to ensure the system is more adapted to your needs; later changes are not allowed (in the prototype)

AIDAVA is using the documents provided by your hospital and data intermediaries. You can only import documents made available by them.

July 2024

AIDAVA: Horizon Europe, Grant 101057062
AI based Data Curation and Publishing Virtual Assistant

19

Figure 2. First Access - Mandatory Steps

3.1.3 Account recovery

Account Recovery

1. If you forget your password, use the Forgot password button on the Login page to recover your account.
2. For any security reason you can change your password in your Account Settings, under the Security and privacy.

In any other situation, contact your study nurse

Figure 3. Account Recovery

3.1.4 Account Settings

Account Settings

Figure 4. Account Settings

3.1.5 Curation Flow

Processing your data: overview

1. Import
(by patient)

2. Curation
(by AI)

3. Answer questions
(by patient and curator)

4. View IPS
(by patient and physician)

Figure 5. Curation Flow

3.1.6 Import

Processing your data: 1. Import

There are documents from your Data Intermediary or the hospital. AIDAVA takes the document(s) you select (by clicking the “+ Add new” button) and imports them for further processing .

Figure 6. Import

3.1.7 Curation

Processing your data: 2. Curation

AIDAVA will process and clean the files you select by clicking the “CURATE” button, and then will insert them into your integrated dossier (called a Personal Health Knowledge Graph). - If there is an issue, AIDAVA may ask you questions.

July 2024

AIDAVA - Horizon Europe, Grant 101057062
AI based Data Curation and Publishing Virtual Assistant

24

Figure 7. Curation

3.1.8 Answer Questions - Patient

Processing your data: 3. Answer Questions

Step 1 Answer Question

Step 2 Confirm Answer

Step 3 Give Feedback

Figure 8. Answer Question - Patient

3.1.9 Answer Question - Curator

Processing your data: 3. Answer Questions

Questions addressed to the patient can be escalated to expert curators

Expert curators can see all previous interactions and all patient and document related information.

Figure 9. Answer Question - Curator

3.1.10 View your dossier (patient view)

Processing your data: 4. Viewing your dossier

After curation, patients are able to view their IPS from the profile

Figure 10. Viewing your “dossier”

3.1.11 Viewing the patient risk score (cardio specialist data users)

Data User - CVD use case

Desktop and Mobile layout

Data users working with cardiovascular disease (CVD) patients will have the capability to calculate a smart risk score using the 'Calculate Smart Risk Score' button. The system will then display the calculated value, duration, and the date of the calculation. Additionally, a green refresh button will enable users to recalculate the score. Furthermore, clicking on the row will reveal a detailed smart risk profile containing all pertinent data.

Figure 11. Data user - CVD view

3.1.12 Viewing the Breast Cancer Registry federated queries across sites (BC data users)

BC Data User - BC use case

Desktop and Mobile layout

Breast cancer specialists have access to the BC registry for calculating metrics. These metrics can be manually recomputed at any given time.

Figure 12. Data user - BC registry view

3.1.13 Viewing the patient dossiers (all data users)

Data User - My Patients view

Desktop and Mobile layout

Figure 13. Data user - Complete Patient view

3.2 Testing results

Testing in G1 focused primarily on user acceptance tests, as the focus is on the frontend, while the focus of G2 is on the backend of the solution and on the curation tools and more in depth testing of these components (unit tests and integration tests) will be required.

3.2.1 Unit tests

Unit tests aim to validate that individual units or components of a software application work as intended. A "unit" typically refers to the smallest testable part of an application, such as a function, method, or class. These tests are crucial for ensuring that each part of the software performs correctly in isolation, providing a foundation for the overall stability and reliability of the application.

Our initial focus was on components directly connected to user actions, as these are the most critical and heavily used parts of the application. Specifically, we concentrated on testing areas such as authentication and data ingestion. These components are essential for ensuring a seamless and secure user experience, as they handle user verification and the input of critical data into the system.

In the subsequent phase, G2, our focus will shift towards testing other vital aspects of the application, including curation tools related to input/output operations and error handling. G2 aims to ensure that the application can manage data correctly and handle unexpected scenarios gracefully. By thoroughly testing these components, we aim to enhance the application's robustness and reliability, ultimately improving the overall user experience and system performance.

3.2.2 Integration tests

Integration tests focused on testing combined functionalities based on synthetic data gathered by the different evaluation sites.

An important part of the time was spent in working with the sites to ensure their synthetic data was as rich and representative of real patient records as possible, and that they would be compliant with the Data Transfer Specification as provided in the Data Source Catalogue. A data validation checker was developed to help sites identify and correct issues; the same tool will be used with real patient data to ensure that data extracted from the data sources are compliant with the Data Transfer Specification.

When synthetic data were ready, the GND team initiated testing going through the process (ingestion, curation, publishing) and identifying issues with different components. Whenever an issue was encountered, the GND team identified the issues and worked with the team responsible for the components to correct the problem. The component was then reintegrated and retested.

At the time of delivering this document, all components were tested at least partially. As the quality of the integration test is directly related to the richness of the synthetic data and these data were limited in scope, we could not manage all components thoroughly. This was expected for G1, and will be solved for G2: we will request all sites, the authorization to automatically generate synthetic data from the patient data collected during G1. This will allow a richer set of synthetic data.

3.2.3 User Acceptance tests

Section 2.1 of *Deliverable D3.2 - Epics and user stories for G1*, describes the approach we took to transfer the user requirements defined in *Deliverable D1.3 - Business Requirements* into user stories and how we developed acceptance criteria that could be measured.

The table below provides an example related to the requirement ID: C0042, belonging to the Epic 02_Curation, for the expert curator. The requirement states: “ *As an expert curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I want AIDAVA to offer me the option to answer the questions of the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant all together at a specific point in time (daily preferably) so that the rest of the time I can still proceed with my usual work*” .

The table below shows the original requirement ID, the acceptance criteria defined in D1.3 and the modified acceptance criteria defined in D3.2, including additional acceptance criteria that were considered as needed to ensure the original requirements could be properly tested.

The same approach was taken across all business requirements and user stories.

Original Req ID	Acceptance Criterium ID	Acceptance Criterion	MODIFIED Acceptance Criterium
UM/MU G-DC014	AC0042.1	The system sends notifications to the curator's AIDAVA account if there are open curation questions to answer.	The system allows the user to specify in its user profile at which time of the day he/she is ready to answer questions (rather than to have them popping up during the whole day)
	AC0042.2	The system provides on the dashboard of the curator's AIDAVA account a button/link to display the open questions (which still need answers from the curator) on the screen	When there is an issue to be answered by a curator, the system checks if this is happening at the time where the curator mentioned he/she is available. If yes, the system initiates a HITL dialogue
	AC0042.3	The system displays a list of all open questions needing curation on the screen.	In case a question is raised and not answered, the system must decide if the curation workflow must be stopped or can continue
	AC0042.4	(new, not existing in D1.3)	The system provides on the dashboard of the curator's AIDAVA account a button/link to display the open questions (which still need answers from the curator) on the screen
	AC0042.5	(new, not existing in D1.3)	If the curator is not available to answer a question (not appropriate time, not present, no answer), the system keeps the issue in a log file the issue
	AC0042.6	(new, not existing in D1.3)	When the systems record an entry in the log file it includes (1) where in the workflow this happened (to allow for easy restart when the answer is provided - if the workflow was stopped, (2) a flag with the type of issue - e.g. coming from a patient, need medical expert,...

Original Req ID	Acceptance Criterium ID	Acceptance Criterion	MODIFIED Acceptance Criterium
	AC0042.7	(new, not existing in D1.3)	There is a small icon on the curator screen with the log of issues to be solved. When there is an open issue in the log, the icon changes colour/get a flag.. (" you have got mail"?)
	AC0042.8	(new, not existing in D1.3)	If the log of issue to be solved is not empty, at the available time mentioned by the curator, the system sends an email to tell him/her that there are issues to be solved
	AC0042.9	(new, not existing in D1.3)	Upon request by the user curator, the system displays a list of all open questions needing curation and allow the user to answer them (and restart the workflow)

The modified acceptance criteria served as the basis for user testing. Dedicated testers from GND undertook the following steps: once the user story was completed by the developer, they checked each user acceptance criterion and determined whether it passed or failed. For any failed acceptance criteria, they created bug tickets detailing the issues. During this period, the user story status reverted to "in progress." Upon resolution of all tasks and bugs, the testers retested the user story according to the acceptance criteria.

3.2.4 Testing non-functional requirements

In the case of non-functional requirements (see Section 3.2 of *Deliverable D1.3 - Business requirements*), we identified those that needed to be fulfilled during development and planned accordingly. These requirements included usability, general design (covering aspects such as language, platform, and integration), regulatory and compliance requirements, and security and data privacy.

Some of these requirements - including maintainability, such as the creation of user manuals, and performance, which involved measuring response time and throughput using various tools - were completed as soon as the application stabilised as the final version for G1. Availability requirements are intended to be assessed after the G1 evaluation by reviewing the issue tickets recorded in our ticketing system.

3.3 Prototype deployment & availability

The table below describes the status of deployment across the 4 evaluation sites

	MUG	NEMC	UM	Maastro
Internal Testing - with synthetic	Done	Done		Done

data				
URL	https://pwa.mug.aidava.eu/	https://admin.nemc.aidava.eu/		https://admin.mastro.aidava.eu/
Handover	Done	Done		Done

Table 1. AIDAVA G1 is deployed

3.3.1 MUG - Medizinische Universität Graz (MUG)

Figure 14. AIDAVA is available in Medizinische Universität Graz (MUG)

3.3.2 NEMC - Sihtasutus Pohja-eeesti Regionaalhaigla

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `pwa.nemc.aidava.eu/auth/(login//secondary:placeholder-image)`. The page content includes:

- AIDAVA** logo at the top left.
- Log in** heading in the center.
- Email** label above a text input field.
- Password** label above a password input field with a lock icon.
- Forgot password?** link below the password field.
- Log in** button in a dark blue rounded rectangle.
- Don't have an account, register** link below the button.
- Any issues? Contact us** or read the **FAQ** link at the bottom.

Figure 14. AIDAVA is available in Sihtasutus Pohja-eeesti Regionaalhaigla (NEMC)

3.3.3 Maastr

← → ↻ 🏠 📄 pwa.maastricht.aidava.eu/auth/(login//secondary:placeholder-image)

Log in

Email

Password

[Forgot password?](#)

Log in

[Don't have an account, register](#)

Any issues? [Contact us](#) or read the [FAQ](#)

Figure 17. AIDAVA is available in Maastricht

3.4 AIDAVA Support

For the evaluation period of G1, we are using the Mantis ticketing system. Each instance has a separate project in the system, allowing every issue, bug, and possible improvement to be tracked. We have three different support levels: Level 1 is for the medical partners who are in contact with the

patients, Level 2 is GND, who will analyse the problem and investigate the root cause, and Level 3 involves the creators of the different curation tools, if an issue with those tools is identified.

Level	WHO	WHAT	HOW
L1	Site Admin	<p>Initial level of support provided to users locally – taking into account local constraints and data privacy. It typically involves basic troubleshooting and issue resolution. The goal is to resolve customer issues as quickly and efficiently as possible</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Answer common questions, provide instructions, or direct customers to self-help resources. • User management: add, update or delete user profiles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Register new user – including personal address – with role and respective access rights; allocate users to roles ○ Take care of users who forgot their password • Log request in Issue Log when not possible to solve the problem directly, and follow up on resolution Note: to send an email from the local site, the AIDAVA local system needs to have access to the local email server (or to have a local account from the hospital email system) • Transfer issue to level 2 when not possible to solve locally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal email, chat, or phone • Local language • 8 to 5 local time, working days <p>Input in Issue Log, required when transferring to L2</p>
L2	GND	<p>Involves more complex issue resolution and may require specialised technical knowledge or expertise. Level 2 support is usually provided by a specialised team, such as a technical support team or an engineering team, and may involve more in-depth troubleshooting or debugging</p> <p>Note: need access to the local version: console level access / IP Secure access with admin rights for maintenance purposes => GND will be an agreed stakeholder (as defined in the Study Protocol)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email and GND phone (remote support with local access) • English • Working days – 8 to 5 local times (CET and CET + 1) = 8 to 6 (CET+1) for GND (NOT 24/7)
L3	GND, UM, ONTO	<p>Involves the most complex and critical issue resolution, such as bug fixes or product enhancements. Level 3 support is usually provided by the product development team or senior technical experts and may involve code changes or product updates.</p>	
L2	HDI	<p>For issues related to access to personal records (IPS) sent to the HDI</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email • English • Working days – 8 to 5 local times (CET and CET + 1)

4 Conclusion and next steps

Deployment of G1 is a critical milestone in the AIDAVA project, enabling first formal evaluation across the 4 evaluation hospitals with real patients, with patient informed consent and following a strict evaluation protocol agreed by local Ethical committees. At the time of writing this deliverable it was successfully deployed in 3 of the 4 evaluation hospitals; it expected to be deployed by mid-July in the 4th evaluation hospital.

In the upcoming period during the G1 evaluation, we will continuously monitor the system and promptly review and resolve any issues that arise with the data and the system.

Based on preliminary testing of the system, it seems that the front end is meeting user expectations (as confirmed during the May 14 Dry Run evaluation workshop with patient consultants). However, as the curation tools had to rely on existing - suboptimal tools - it is expected that the quality of the resulting curated data (i.e. the Personal Health Knowledge Graph) will be suboptimal and will not contain all the data that should be extracted from the source data. We will thoroughly assess this aspect as part of the evaluation and identify how to improve the performance of these tools for Generation 2 (G2) of the prototype.

After evaluation we will progress on the following aspects of G2 of the prototype.

- **Update of requirement for G2.** The result of evaluation of G1 will be taken into account for the update of the business requirements, and user stories. These updated requirements will be checked, impact on the prototype for change will be assessed and changes will be executed.
- **Integration of newly developed/improved components.** Several new/updated AI curation and data quality enhancement tools will be replaced in G2. One of key difficulties in G1 was the integration and testing of multiple components across different teams. Considering that many of the new components to be integrated are AI-based tools, it is critical that they comply with the requirements for testing of the emerging AI Act regulation. As a result for G2 we decided to put in place a formal process before integrating any new components. This will include the following points that will be documented as well into the library of curation tools.
 - Specification of expected input and expected output (content, semantic, syntax)
 - High level description of the intended use and expected behaviour - including key assumptions
 - Test data and approach to testing as independent module (specifically important for AI based module)
 - Results of test before integration as an independent module. This last aspect is particularly important to ensure that the whole prototype can be considered as tested and trustworthy, indeed a whole is as reliable as its weakest part.
- **In depth testing of quality and completeness of the resulting PHKG.** The Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG), representing the personal longitudinal health record, is the result of the integration and curation of multiple Source Health Knowledge Graph (SHKG). Each SHKG is the result of the curation on one single data source, with potentially several curation tools and more or less manual intervention through the HTIL dialogue. The resulting PHKG will be compared with a data quality score as described in Deliverable D4.6. In addition we

will perform manual data quality check with the improved tools developed for G2, i.e. we will check manually several carefully selected data sources: we will extract manually the concepts that are expected to be included in the SHKG and then compare with the results provided by the AIDAVA prototype G2. In case of discrepancies we will analyse the reason (human error in the manual SHKG or algorithmic mistake in the AIDAVA generated SHKG).